

CF Compliance errors in the CMIP6 archive

Ruth Petrie, Fran Eggleton, Martin Jukes

Corresponding author: martin.jukes@physics.ox.ac.uk

The table below lists errors encountered when running quality control tests on data which had been published in the WCRP CMIP6 archive prior to importing it into the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS). Although the prevalence of technical errors is significant, most of the data was passed for acceptance in the CDS after review because it could be established with some confidence that the errors would not affect the planned applications. Attribute names which start with an underscore are, for instance, invalid according to the CF Conventions, but are ignored silently by most software applications. It is, however, impossible to rule out an impact as some software may reject data which is compromised by CF compliance errors.

CF Compliance Error Message	Severity	Comment
Attribute missing_value of incorrect type (expecting 'Data Variable' type, got 'Numeric' type)	Minor	This error occurs if, for example, the data variable is double precision and the missing_value variable is single precision.
(4.3.3): formula_terms attribute only allowed on coordinate variables	Minor	
(7.1): Boundary var time_bnds has inconsistent calendar to time	Minor	
(3.1): Units are not consistent with those given in the standard_name table.	Minor	
(3.1): Units are not consistent with those given in the standard_name table.	Minor	This error occurs on a height variable which is used as an ancillary coordinate.
(3.1): Units are not consistent with those given in the standard_name table.	Minor	
Invalid attribute name: _CoordinateAxisType	Minor	
(7.2): Invalid cell_measures syntax	Minor	
(3.3): Invalid standard_name: alevel	NA	
(7.1): Boundary var lev_bnds has inconsistent standard_name to lev', '(3.1): Units are not consistent with those given in the standard_name table.', '(4.3.3): formula_terms attribute only allowed on coordinate variables	NA	
(2.6.3): Variable volcello named as an external variable must not be present in this file	NA	
(2.6.3): Variable volcello named as an external variable must not be present in this file	NA	

(7.3): Invalid syntax for cell_methods attribute	NA	
(3.3): Invalid standard_name: olevel	NA	
(3.3): Invalid standard_name: ocean_sigma_z'	Minor	
(5): Dimensions must be a subset of dimensions of thetaoga	Minor	
(7.3): Invalid 'name' in cell_methods attribute: scalar_axis	Minor	
(7.2): cell_measures variable areacello must either exist in this netCDF file or be named by the external_variables attribute	Minor	
(3.3): Invalid standard_name: bounds	Major	
(3.3): Invalid standard_name: Vertical', '(3.3): Invalid standard_name modifier: levels	Minor	
(3.3): Invalid standard_name: Vertical', '(3.3): Invalid standard_name modifier: levels	Minor	
(7.1): Boundary var lev_bnds has inconsistent units to lev	Minor	
(3.3): Invalid standard_name: ocean_sigma_z', '(4.3.3): formula_terms attribute only allowed on coordinate variables', '(4.3.3): No formula defined for standard name: ocean_sigma_z	Major	
(3.3): Invalid region name: atlantic_arctic_extended_ocean	Minor	
(4.3.3): Formula term nsigma not present in formula for ocean_sigma_z_coordinate	Minor	
(4.3.3): formula_terms attribute only allowed on coordinate variables', '(4.3.3): Formula term nsigma not present in formula for ocean_sigma_z_coordinate	NA	
(4.3.3): formula_terms attribute only allowed on coordinate variables', '(4.3.3): ps is not declared as a variable	Minor	
(5): Dimensions must be a subset of dimensions of volo	Minor	
(7.2): cell_measures variable areacella must either exist in this netCDF file or be named by the external_variables attribute	NA	
(2.6.3): Variable areacella named as an external variable must not be present in this file	Minor	
(2.6.3): Variable areacella named as an external variable must not be present in this file	NA	
(5): Dimensions must be a subset of dimensions of siarean	Minor	
(5): Dimensions must be a subset of dimensions of siareas	NA	
(5): Dimensions must be a subset of dimensions of sivoln	Minor	
(5): Dimensions must be a subset of dimensions of sivol	NA	
(3.3): Invalid standard_name: Latitude', '(3.3): Invalid standard_name modifier: axis	Major	
(3.3): Invalid region name: g', '(3.3): Invalid region name: a	Minor	
(3.3): Variable basin of invalid type. Region variable should be of type char.	Minor	
(7.3): Invalid unit hours, in cell_methods comment	Minor	
(7.1): bounds attribute referencing non-existent variable sdepth_bnds	NA	
(3.3): Invalid syntax for 'standard_name' attribute: 'number of layers'	Minor	

(3.3): Invalid region name: caribbean_windward_passage', '(3.3): Invalid region name: taiwan_and_luzon_straits', '(3.3): Invalid region name: agulhas_section	Minor	
(4.3.3): formula_terms attribute only allowed on coordinate variables', '(4.3.3): ap_bnds is not declared as a variable', '(4.3.3): b_bnds is not declared as a variable', '(4.3.3): ps is not declared as a variable	Minor	
(7.3): Invalid 'name' in cell_methods attribute: y", "(7.3): Invalid 'name' in cell_methods attribute: x	Major	
(7.1): bounds attribute referencing non-existent variable lat_bnds	Minor	
(7.1): bounds attribute referencing non-existent variable lon_bnds	Minor	
(3.3): Invalid region name: a', '(3.3): Invalid region name: i', '(3.3): Invalid region name: g	Minor	
(2.3): Invalid variable name	Minor	
(5): co-ordinate variable not monotonic	Minor	

Table 12: CF compliance issues detected in the CMIP6 archive. Based on an analysis of data evaluated for publication in the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store. Further work is needed to repeat the test on the variables identified in the baseline variable list and engage with data providers to mitigate the risk of errors being repeated. Errors have been classified as "Major" or "Minor" according to their assessment significance for the intended range of use cases in the C3S Climate Data Store. In many cases this is because the error message has been triggered by an ancillary variable rather than by metadata directly associated with the primary data variable and its coordinates. Errors are marked as "NA" when they apply to files which were excluded from C3S publication for other reasons (e.g. because the data is on an unstructured grid).